

Assessment of the Effectiveness of Folical, A Physio-Activator of Plant Origin in the Treatment of Blossom-End Rot in Tomato Crops

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Abstract

The tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) is a fruit vegetable that is widely consumed in Ivory Coast. However, its production is severely limited by Blossom-end rot, one of the most constraining abiotic diseases of tomato cultivation in some production areas of the country. The present work was initiated to evaluate the effectiveness of the physio-activator "Folical", based on algae extract (*Ascophyllum nodosum*), which is composed of GA 14 and 202.5 g/L of calcium oxide, in the treatment of Blossom-end rot of tomatoes. To achieve this objective, a trial was carried out on soil potentially deficient in calcium and magnesium. The optimal dose of Folical for efficient reduction of Blossom-end rot incidence was determined. The efficacy of this dose was compared with that of two reference products. The doses of Folical 4 L/ha, 5 L/ha and 6 L/ha as well as the recommended doses (0.25 L/ha and 109.4 Kg/ha) and tap water (product-free controls) were applied by foliar spraying in a completely randomized Fisher block system with three replicates. The doses of Folical had significant effects on reducing the rate of attacked plants and Blossom-end rot fruits. The rates of 5 L/ha and 6 L/ha, which gave the lowest rates of attacked plants, 29.36% and 37.42% respectively, also resulted in a reduction in the incidence of Blossom-end rot fruits in treated plants, which were 4.85% and 5.47% respectively, compared to the reference products; Codamin (8.4%) and Calcium Nitrate (13.78%), and the untreated control (27.48%). The 5 L/ha dose of Folical recorded the lowest fruit growth rate of 6.42% and the average weight of the highest fruit was 94.8 g. The doses of 5 L/ha and 6 L/ha of bio activator were the most effective in the treatment of tomato Blossom-end rot.

Keywords : Bio-activator, Abiotic stress, Blossom-end rot, Ivory Coast, Tomato

1. INTRODUCTION

In Ivory Coast, tomato cultivation in the green house and the field is subject to numerous diseases, both parasitic and physiological (Ahébé Marie Hélène *et al.*, 2021). The latter constitute a major constraint to tomato production (Tonetto de Freitas *et al.*, 2011). Among these physiological diseases, a Blossom-end rot of the fruit is responsible for huge production losses as it leads to a depreciation of the commercial quality of the fruit (Sun, Feng, et Liu 2013; Taylor, Locascio, et Alligood, 2004; Suzuki, Shono, et Egawa 2003; Casado-Vela, Sellés, et Bru Martínez 2005). To combat this deficiency, market gardeners often resort to the use of synthetic pesticides whose recommended application rates are generally not respected and are abused (Ngk *et al.*, 2021; Son *et al.* 2017). Moreover, the use of these pesticides contributes to environmental pollution, the intoxication of the producers themselves and the deterioration of consumer health due to chemical residues (De Saeger *et al.*, 2020). The over use of synthetic products also leads to the resistance of harmful insects and the destruction of beneficial insects (Christian *et al.*, 2019; . Yarou *et al.*, 2017 ; Kodjo *et al.*, 2012 ; Ait Taadaouit *et al.*, 2012). To find more efficient and less restrictive control solutions, the stimulation of mineral uptake and metabolism in tomato by physio-activators is a more ecological alternative (De Saeger *et al.*, 2020; Nephali *et al.*, 2020; Ali, Ramsuhag, et Jayaraman, 2019; Aghofack, Schinzoumka, et Tatchago, 2015). The general objective of this study is to reduce the incidence of blossom-end rot in

tomato crops by the application of Folical, a plant extract-based physio-activator. To achieve this objective, activities to determine the optimal dose were carried out and the efficacy of the said dose was compared to that of some reference products registered in Ivory Coast against tomato Blossom-end rot.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Experimental site

The trial was carried out in Songon Té, an important tomato production area in Ivory Coast. This locality is located in the lagoon region between 004°14'37.1" W longitude and 05°18'35.0" N latitude with an altitude of 7 m. Songon Té is located about 29 km west of the city of Abidjan on the Abidjan-Dabou road. The climate is hot and humid sub-equatorial (Eldin, 1971). It is characterised by four seasons long dry season lasting two months from January to February, a long rainy season lasting five months from March to July, a short dry season in August and a short rainy season from September to December. The soils are ferritic and sandy-clay. During the trial, the average temperature was 34°C with a relative humidity of 55% (dry season). The site of the experiment is a low land.

2.2. Physico-chemical characterisation of the soil

Soil samples were taken by hand auger at depth of 0-20 cm from the four corners and the centre of the plot (Kone *et al.*, 2010). These sub-samples were then mixed to obtain a 1/kg composite sample (Ballot *et al.*, 2016). The composite soil sample (1 kg) was air-dried at room temperature in the laboratory for seven days. After drying, the soil was crushed using porcelain mortar and pestle before being sieved on a 2 mm mesh screen. After sieving, the sub-sieve was used for Physico-chemical analyses (Dosso and Kone 2016). Soil particle size characterisation was carried out using the ROBINSON pipette method and soil texture was assessed using the USDA textural triangle or textural diagram. The pH water and KCl were determined with a glass electrode in a ratio of 1:2.5 as described by Thomas (1996) and cited by (Akassimadou and Yao-Kouamé 2014). EC was determined using a glass electrode conductivity meter in a ratio of 1:5 at 25°C. The organic matter content was determined by the loss on ignition method. The organic carbon (OC) content of the soil was deduced from the organic matter (OM) content according to the formula of Golueke 1977 cited by M'Sadak and Saad, 2015.

$$\% CO = \frac{\% MO}{1,8}$$

Total phosphorus was determined by the method described by Olsen and Sommers (1982). Exchangeable bases (Na, Ca, Mg and K) and iron (Fe) were determined by extraction with buffered ammonium acetate at pH 7.0 before atomic absorption (Ca, Mg and Fe) and flame spectrometer (Na and K) readings. Total nitrogen (total N) was determined by the Kjeldahl method (Bremner, 1996).

2.3. Vegetable material

The plant material consisted of tomato plants (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) of the commercial variety Caraïbo. This variety is characterised by round fruits with an average weight of 100 g and a bright red colour at harvest. It is the most cultivated variety in the Songon locality and is susceptible to apical necrosis (CEPROSEM, 2015).

2.4. Experimental design

After 21 days in the nursery, the tomato plants were transplanted at the three-leaf stage. The design used was a completely randomised Fisher block with three replicates. Each replication was subdivided into six elementary plots or treatments. Each treatment had 30 plants arranged in a double row on a 6 m long ridge. The spacing between plants in the row was 0.4 m and 0.5 m between rows. The ridges were spaced 0.8 m apart, giving a density of 31250 plants/ha.

2.5. Crop management and treatments

Watering was done once every two days. Regular weeding was done to control weediness. Urea (100 kg/ha) was applied on day 20 and 50 after transplant. Phytosanitary treatments with Cypercal 50 EC (50 g/L

cypermethrin) were carried out at a rate of 0.8 L/ha to control insects. Two applications were made the first during the vegetative phase and the last at the beginning of fruiting. To control cryptogamic diseases, a binary fungicide composed of chlorothalonil (550 g/L) and carbendazim (100 g/L) was used. Two applications were made during the vegetative phase and one application was made during fruiting. These phytosanitary treatments were done on a warning basis.

The physio-activator tested is Folical. Its active ingredients are GA 14 and calcium oxide. It was tested at three different doses 4 L/ha, 5 L/ha and 6 L/ha. These doses were respectively treatments T1, T2 and T3 and compared to the controls Codamin B-MO (T4) and Calcium Nitrate (T5), which are respectively a growth regulator and a fertiliser used in the control of apical necrosis of tomato in Ivory Coast. Codamin has two active ingredients, boron and molybdenum. They stimulate the physiological functions of flowering and fruit set. The second control is composed of 15% nitrogen and 28% calcium oxide. Table 1 show the characteristics of the products used and the different doses applied.

Before each application, a plant health analysis was carried out to determine the level of infestation in the plot. For each treatment, except for calcium nitrate, the necessary amount of product was dissolved in 10 litres of water. This spray was applied to the plants, targeting the fruits and leaves. Calcium nitrate was applied around the plant at a rate of 3.5 g/plant while avoiding direct contact with the plant. The applications started when the first fruits were formed, i.e. 46 days after transplanting the plants. Thereafter, an application was made every 15 days under the same conditions and 3 applications were made during the fruiting period.

2.6. Plant development cycle

Observations on the development cycle of the plants focused on the different phenological dates; 50% flowering, fruit shedding after maturity and time to first harvest (Coulibaly *et al.*, 2019). These dates were used to determine the earliness, length of the crop cycle. The 50% flowering date is the number of days from sowing to the day when 50% of the transplanted plants have flowered. This variable is evaluated days after sowing (DAS). The date of the first harvest (sowing - first harvest) represents the number of days from sowing to the day when the first harvest of ripe fruit is made. This variable, expressed as the number of DAS measures the earliness of the variety tested. The date on which the first change in colour of the mature fruit was observed was also expressed in DAS. The number of days between the date of the first harvest and the date of the last harvest gives the duration of production in days (Fondio *et al.*, 2013 and Djidji *et al.*, 2010).

2.7. Fruit growth

To monitor the effect of the different treatments on fruit growth, five fruits were selected per treatment. The diametrical growth of these fruits was assessed using calliper. Data were collected weekly from fruits set to harvest. The fruit was assumed to be set when the diameter was equal to 0.5 cm. The fruit growth index was given by the ratio I.

$$I = \frac{(Dt - D \text{ fruit set})}{D \text{ fruit set}}$$

D fruit set : Average diameter of fruit at fruit set

Dt : Average fruit diameter at time.

2.8. Rate of affected plants

Before the first application of the products, all plants with at least one Blossom-end rot fruit were counted and marked with an indelible marker. After 7 days, and before the next application of the products, the new plants with Blossom-end rot fruits were counted and marked. The rate of attacked plants was calculated according to the following formula :

$$RAP (\%) = \frac{\text{Nber PA}}{\text{Nber PF}} \times 100$$

Nber PA : Number of plants attacked ;

Nber PF : Total number of plants bearing at least one fruit ;

RAP : Rate of attacked plants.

The cumulative rate of attacked plants was calculated by summing the weekly rates of attacked plants.

2.9. Rate of Blossom-end rot fruit

Before the first application of the products, all Blossom-end rot fruits were counted and marked with an indelible marker. After 7 days, and before the next application of the products, the new Blossom-end rot fruits were counted and marked. The rate of Blossom-end rot fruits was calculated according to the formula used by R'HIM and JEBARI (2008) in similar studies.

$$NFR (\%) = \frac{\text{Nber FN}}{\text{Nber TF}} \times 100$$

Nber FN : Number of Blossom-end rot fruits

Nber TF : Total number of fruits ;

NFR : Blossom-end rot fruit rate.

This parameter was also assessed at each harvest and an accumulation was made after the four harvests.

2.10. Evaluation of the effectiveness of treatments at harvest

At each harvest, yield components were determined from the number and mass of healthy and damaged fruit. The number of fruits harvested was determined by counting. Spoiled fruit was separated from healthy fruit. Their number and mass were also determined:

2.10.1. Average weight of a fruit

At each harvest, all fruits were weighed using a 0.05 kg precision scale. The average fruit weight was calculated per treatment according to the following formula :

$$\text{Average weight of a fruit } AVF (g) = \frac{\text{Total mass of the fruits } TMF}{NFH}$$

AWF : Average weight of fruit

TMF : Total mass of the fruits

NFH : Number of fruits harvested

2.10.2. Average yield

At the end of the fourth and final harvest, the cumulative values were calculated. The average yield for each plot was calculated and reported per hectare using the expression below:

$$\text{Average yield} = \frac{31250 \text{ plants} \times MTHFH}{90 \text{ plants}}$$

31250 plants is the density per hectare

MTHFH : Mass in tonnes of healthy fruits harvested from the 90 plants

90 plants is the total number of plants for each treatment.

2.11. Statistical analysis

The collected data were subjected to an analysis of variance (ANOVA) using STATISTICA Version 2006.7.1 software to detect significant differences between the means. These means were compared using Fisher's LSD test at the 5% level to group treatments with similar effects.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Physico-chemical characterisation of the soil

The granulometric analyses of the soil showed high levels of sand (40.68%) and very low levels of clay (0.08%) and silt (0.003%). The texture of the soil was sandy loam with the presence of light sandy silt. The soil at the study site is moderately acidic (pH water = 6.05) and very rich in organic matter (OM = 58.4%). It also has a C/N ratio (40.13) that is completely above the norm. Minerals such as phosphorus, potassium, sodium and calcium have excessive values, while magnesium is deficient (0.2 me/100g) in the soil. The cation exchange capacity (35.06 me/100g) is also higher than the norm (Table 1). In this soil, the exchange complex is almost saturated (V = 87.96%). The results of the different equilibria between the minerals and the saturation rates per exchangeable base on the adsorbent complex are recorded in Table 2. The values of the ratios (Ca²⁺/K⁺ = 0.91) and (Ca²⁺/Na⁺ = 0.73) are low. These results suggest that there is a calcium deficiency in potassium and sodium as well. However, the Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺ and K⁺/Mg²⁺ ratios show a deficiency of magnesium on potassium and calcium in the soil. On the other hand, the fertility index (Ca²⁺ + Mg²⁺) /K⁺, Ca²⁺/CEC and Mg²⁺/CEC are very low in contrast to the percentage of exchangeable sodium (Na⁺/CEC) and exchangeable potassium (K⁺/CEC) which showed excessive values. Potassium and sodium are in excess on the adsorbent complex while calcium is deficient.

Parameters	Values	Standards *
Clay (%)	0,08	-
Silt (%)	0,003	-
Sand (%)	40,68	-
Porosity (%)	7,82	-
field capacity (%)	17,06	-
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	0,57	-
Electric conductivity (µs/cm)	42,19	-
pH water	6,05	5 - 6
pH KCl	4,21	4 - 5
Δ pH	1,84	-
OM (%)	58,4	3,6 - 6,5
CO (%)	33,87	1,26 - 2,5
N (%)	0,85	0,12 - 0,22
C/N	40,13	11 - 15
P (%)	0,27	0,02 - 0,023
K ⁺ (mél/100g)	9,63	0,15 - 0,25
Na ⁺ (mél/100g)	12,17	0,3 - 0,7
Ca ²⁺ (mél/100g)	8,83	5 - 8
Mg ²⁺ (mél/100g)	0,2	1,5 - 3,0
Fe (mg/kg)	1,83	-
SBE (mél/100g)	30,85	7,5 - 15
CEC (mél/100g)	35,06	10 ≤ CEC ≤ 20
V (%)	87,96	60 ≤ V ≤ 90

Table 1. Particle size composition and chemical characteristics of the study site soil**3.2. Plant development cycle**

The plants flowered 55 days after sowing (DAS). Fruit dehiscence was observed 85 days after sowing. Harvesting started at 95 days after sowing and was completed at 116 days after sowing. The total duration of production was 21 days.

Δ pH :pH variation; OM: Organic matter; OC: Organic carbon; SBE: Sum of exchangeable bases; CEC: Cation exchange capacity; V: Saturation rate of the adsorbent complex ;*Reference threshold values (Ballot *et al.*, 2016)

Parameters	Values	Standards *
$\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{K}^+$	0,91	-
$\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Na}^+$	0,73	-
$\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Mg}^{2+}$	43,2	2 - 9
$\text{K}^+/\text{Mg}^{2+}$	47	0,05 - 0,1
$(\text{Na}^+ + \text{Mg}^{2+})/\text{Ca}^{2+}$	1,42	-
$(\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+})/\text{K}^+$	1,28	12 - 15
SAR	2,73	-
$\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{CEC}$ (%)	25,11	60 - 70
$\text{Mg}^{2+}/\text{CEC}$ (%)	0,59	10 - 12
Na^+/CEC (%)	34,79	< 1
K^+/CEC (%)	27,46	2,5 - 3,5

Table 2. Cationic balance and exchangeable base saturation rate on the soil adsorbent complex

SAR : Sodium Adsorption Ratio ; *Reference threshold values (Ballot *et al.*, 2016)

3.3.Fruit growth

The treatments significantly modified fruit growth. Indeed, treatment T2 (5 L of Folical per ha) showed the lowest growth index ($I = 3.72$) from fruit set to harvest (Figure 1). While treatment T1 gave the highest growth index ($I = 4.58$) from fruit set to harvest. Treatments T0, T1, T3, T4 and T5 were not significantly different.

3.4. Rate of affected plants

Analysis of the data collected per week showed that the control treatment (T0) had the highest percentage of plants with Blossom-end rot fruit over the 7 weeks of observation. The analysis of variance showed a significant difference between the rates of affected plants of the different treatments during the first four weeks of observation. At the end of the observations, the data were cumulated. The analysis of variance showed a highly significant difference between the rates of attacked plants of the different treatments (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Effect of treatments on fruit growth index

Figure 2. Effect of treatments on the rate of plants bearing at least one fruit with Blossom-end rot at harvest.

3.4. Rate of Blossom-end rot fruit

The rate of Blossom-end rot fruits was highly significant in the 2nd and 6th week of observation. In the other weeks (S1, S3, S4, and S7) there was a significant difference between treatments. Figure 3A shows the rate of Blossom-end rot fruits obtained per treatment at the end of the observations. The percentages of Blossom-end rot fruits per treatment were significantly different and distributed in four classes. Treatments T2 and T3 had the lowest rates of Blossom-end rot fruit and constituted the first class. The second class included treatment T1. Treatments T4 and T5 were intermediate to the two previous classes. The last class included treatment T0 with 3.93% Blossom-end rot. The effect of the treatments on the rate of Blossom-end rot fruit was also analysed at the end of the harvest. Indeed, a highly significant difference ($p = 0.0035$) was obtained between the different treatments. They were grouped into different homogeneous groups (Figure 3B).

Figure 3. effect of treatments on the rate of Blossom-end rot fruit during the seven weeks of evaluation (A) and after four harvests (B).

3.5.Fruit diameter

No significant differences were observed between treatments for the average fruit diameter (Figure 4). However, treatment T5 (calcium nitrate) had the highest average fruit diameter (5.78 cm) and treatment T2 (Folical 5 L/ha) the lowest (5.06 cm).

Figure 4. effect of treatments on average fruit diameter at harvest

3.6. Yield components

For the average fruit weight, the analysis of variance indicates that there is no significant difference between treatments. However, it can be seen that the average fruit weight varied between 86.46 g for T0 and 94.8 g for T2 (Table 3). In terms of average yield and potential yield, the effect of treatments was not significant, although numerically it can be observed that treatments T5 and T3 recorded the highest average and potential yields. The average yield was 5.86 t/ha for both treatments. The potential yields were 7.64 t/ha for the T5 treatment and 7.30 t/ha for the T3. Regarding yield loss, treatment T2 recorded the lowest loss (17.06%) followed by treatment T4 with 17.36% (Table 3).

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Treatments	Average weight of fruits (g)	Average yield (t/ha)	Potential yield (t/ha)	Yield losses (%)
T0	86,464 a	3,96 a	6,076 a	34,83
T1	87,433 a	3,403 a	4,907 a	30,65
T2	94,798 a	5,683 a	6,852 a	17,06
T3	91,910 a	5,856 a	7,302 a	19,80
T4	84,448 a	5,347 a	6,470 a	17,36
T5	93,368 a	5,856 a	7,639 a	23,34

Table 3. Average yield according to

*Rates followed by the same letter in the same column are not significantly different at the 5% level according to the LSD test.

4. DISCUSSION

The granulometric analysis of the soil of the experimental site revealed a sandy-silty texture that is most often favourable to tomato cultivation. These results show that the soil at this site is suitable for tomato cultivation. Therefore, if sufficient mineral elements are supplied, there may be no Blossom-end rot. The moderately acidic water pH is also favourable for tomato cultivation but with the risk of slight calcium and magnesium deficiencies. The high organic matter content of the soil gives the soil its peaty appearance. Indeed, high levels of organic matter are generally found in peat soils. The ratio of carbon to nitrogen (C/N = 40.13), which is much higher than the reference standard, indicates poor mineralisation of the organic matter. Calcium levels (8.83 me/100g) in the soil are slightly higher than the normative values (5-8 me/100g). However, the percentage of exchangeable calcium (25.11%) is much lower than the reference standard. This result indicates a low availability of calcium in the soil solution. Consequently, it is very little available to plants, unlike sodium and potassium. This unavailability of calcium could be explained by the massive presence of sodium and potassium ions on the adsorbent complex at the expense of calcium ions. These results showed that there is a marked deficiency of calcium and magnesium. Our results coincide with those of (Ballot *et al.*, 2016) who showed that increasing the concentration of potassium in a nutrient solution decreases the absorption of calcium and magnesium.

The flowering and first harvest dates of 55 days after sowing and 95 days after sowing, respectively, are generally intrinsic genetic traits, specific to the Caraïbo tomato variety. Indeed, these results confirm those of Djidji *et al.*, (2010). These authors showed that the flowering time of the Caraïbo tomato variety is 56 days after sowing and the date of the first harvest is 94 days after sowing. However, our results are contrary to those of Fondio *et al.*, 2013 who showed that the flowering time and first harvest of this tomato variety were respectively 71 JAS and 107 JAS. We note that some varietal genetic traits can be influenced by environmental factors and the cultivation techniques used. The change in fruit colour after maturity seems to be linked to light intensity and insolation. According to Hanson (1996), reduced light intensity and insolation slow down the ripening of the fruit while maintaining its quality. As for the duration of production, which was 21 days, it could be explained by the good sanitary condition of the plot. In addition, Fondio *et al.*, (2013) pointed out that the duration of production depends on the parasitic pressures that act on the development of the plants, thus reducing their production capacity.

Overall, treatment T2 (Folical 5 L/ha) had the lowest growth rate. Unlike the other treatments, this dose of Folical does not cause exponential fruit growth. Therefore, it significantly reduced the rate of attacked plants and necrotic fruits. Regarding the rate of attacked plants, Folical 5 L/ha had a very different effect than the other two doses and the control products. Indeed, the low rate of attacked plants presented by this treatment can be explained by the fact that the plants treated with this dose were less vigorous and presented a much lower above-ground biomass than those of the other treatments. According to some

authors: Aikman and Houter, 1990; Ho, 1993; Morley *et al.*, 1993; Marcelis *et al.*, 1999, plants with high vegetative vigour may reduce calcium transfer to the fruits in favour of transpiring organs, thus leading to the high susceptibility of the fruits to Blossom-end rot. Indeed, the entry of calcium into the plant is linked to the absorption of water by the roots. Water uptake and circulation are closely related to leaf transpiration. Therefore, an organ with a high transpiration rate receives more water and calcium, so the leaves receive greater amounts of calcium than the fruits.

Regarding the rate of necrotic fruits, the effect of the T2 treatment (Folical 5 L/ha) may be due to the growth rate of the fruits and their average diameter. The fruits treated with Folical 5 L/ha had the lowest growth rates during the trial. This explains the low rate of Blossom-end rot fruit recorded with this dose. This treatment did not induce a growth spurt, predisposing the fruit to the occurrence of Blossom-end rot. This result is in agreement with those of Saure (2001) who observed that fruits without a rapid growth phase do not develop apical necrosis. Following the average fruit diameter which was not significant but the T2 treatment had the smallest diameter which also explains the reduction in the rate of Blossom-end rot fruits by this dose of Folical. According to authors such as Mortley *et al.*, 1991, there is a negative correlation between fruit size and calcium concentration. Thus, in large diameter fruits, there is an increase in phloem transport of assimilates without an increase in xylem transport of calcium.

The analysis of yield parameters showed no significant differences between treatments. However, the highest potential yield of 7.64 t/ha for treatment T5 (calcium nitrate) can be explained by the nitrogen content (15%) of calcium nitrate. The average fruit weight (94.8 g) and the yield loss (17.06%) obtained by treatment T2 (Folical 5 L/ha) can be due to the constituents of this physio-activator. Moreover, the Folical physio-activator contains GA 14 cream which is rich in phytohormones (amino acids, polysaccharides...). These molecules seem to stimulate the assimilation of nutrients which are the basis for a quality yield.

CONCLUSION

The doses of the Folical physio-activator 5 L/ha and 6 L/ha were the most efficient in the treatment of Blossom-end rot of tomato. They can therefore be an alternative to chemical products in the perspective of sustainable agriculture, respectful of the environment and the consumer's health.

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